

Yield differences among some deepwater rices (DWRs)

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Most deepwater areas in Thailand are planted to local cultivars. Farmers believe that some characteristics of their traditional DWRs—yielding capacity, internode elongation, growth duration, adaptability, and milling quality—make them most suitable.

We compared the performance of local and improved DWRs under natural field conditions in 1988 and 1989 wet seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

The cultivars were dry seeded onto plowed soil at 120 kg seeds/ha. Seedlings experienced drought stress in late Jul. In late Aug, the water level gradually increased to about 1 m in early Nov. No fertilizer was applied, but routine crop protection was done as needed.

Table 1. Grain yield of 20 deepwater rice cultivars. Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Ayuthaya, Thailand, 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Cultivar	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1988	1989
RD19 ^a	2.7	2.8
Khao Mali	2.7	2.7
Huntra 60 ^a	2.6	3.1
Khao Puang Nak	2.6	2.3
Plai Ngahm	2.5	2.4
Sai Bua	2.4	2.2
SPR7233-32-1-6-1	2.3	
Luang Pratham		2.6
Mali Tawng	2.3	2.5
Khao Kaset	2.3	2.2
Leb Mue Nahng 111	2.3	2.2
Khao Rachinee	2.2	2.7
Sam Ruang	2.2	2.6
Nahng Khiew	2.2	2.5
Pan Tawng	2.2	2.5
Pin Gaew 56 ^a	2.2	2.0
Khao Hoi	2.1	2.0
Khao Lod Chong	2.1	2.4
Ban Daeng	2.1	2.2
Khao Tah Haeng 17	2.0	
Khao Raguad		2.4
Tapow Gaew 161 ^a	1.9	1.8
LSD (0.05)	ns	0.5

^aRecommended deepwater rice variety.

Yield differences are shown in Table 1. Improved plant type cultivars Huntra 60 and RD19 yielded the highest. Recom-

Table 2. Relationship between grain yield and agronomic characteristics of deepwater rice.

Characteristic	1988	1989
Panicles (no./m ²)	+0.65**	+0.83**
Panicle wt (g)	+0.45*	-0.40 ns
Tillers at maturity (no./m ²)	+0.64**	+0.82**
Productive tillers (%)	-0.05 ns	+0.39 ns
Dry matter production (t/ha)	+0.29 ns	-0.10 ns
Harvest index	+0.54*	+0.81**
Height (cm)	-0.10 ns	-0.50*
Growth duration (d)	+0.12 ns	+0.15 ns

mended traditional plant type varieties Pin Gaew 56 and Tapow Gaew 161 yielded the lowest. Local cultivar Khao Mali gave relatively high yields.

In simple linear correlation analysis, grain yields were positively correlated with panicle number and tiller number per unit area and with harvest index, but negatively correlated with plant height (Table 2). Correlations of grain yield with dry matter production, days to maturity, and productive tillers were low. Panicle number, not panicle weight, was the critical factor in higher yields. ■

Genetic studies in the F₂ of crosses for high grain quality

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We evaluated five genetic variables in the F₂ of three crosses (see table). OM576 is from Vietnam, Basmati 370 from India, and IR68 and IR31868-64-2-3-3-3 from IRRI (named OM87-9 in Vietnam). The parents all have good grain quality.

The 1990 wet season experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Selection intensity was about 2% from each population.

Phenotypic and genotypic coefficient of variability (PCV and GCV) showed high values for panicles/hill, grain numbers/panicle, and single plant yield; low value for 1,000-grain weight; and moderate value for plant height. PCV was higher than GCV for all traits.

Genetic parameters of F₂ of 3 crosses for grain quality.^a

Character	Cross	Mean	SD	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	h ² (%)	GA (% of mean)
Plant height (cm)	OM576/Basmati 370	121.3	16.3	6.8	9.3	54.0	12.2
	IR68/Basmati 370	109.7	5.5	2.8	7.5	14.1	2.6
	OM87-9/IR68	107.0	4.4	3.4	7.9	18.2	3.5
Panicles/hill	OM576/Basmati 370	20.3	10.2	26.9	33.0	67.0	53.5
	IR68/Basmati 370	17.3	5.5	13.1	26.0	25.0	26.0
	OM87-9/IR68	13.7	1.2	25.7	38.3	45.2	41.7
Grains/panicle	OM576/Basmati 370	85.1	36.9	22.1	30.1	54.2	39.3
	IR68/Basmati 370	88.7	7.9	10.1	22.0	21.0	11.2
	OM87-9/IR68	91.5	5.1	10.5	21.7	23.4	7.2
1000-grain weight (g)	OM576/Basmati 370	24.7	1.1	1.4	4.8	8.1	0.0
	IR68/Basmati 370	25.4	1.3	0.4	4.9	1.5	0.0
	OM87-9/IR68	25.7	1.8	2.9	5.7	26.0	3.6
Single plant yield (g)	OM576/Basmati 370	15.2	1.5	37.2	44.4	70.0	75.1
	IR68/Basmati 370	12.5	3.0	9.8	31.2	10.0	7.5
	OM87-9/IR68	10.6	1.3	18.9	39.7	23.3	22.1

^ah² = broad-sense heritability, GA = genetic advance.

Grain weight had low broad-sense heritability and low genetic advance, indicating nonadditive gene action.

Very high values of heritability and genetic advance were obtained, especially in OM576/Basmati 370. This indicates

that additive gene action had more influence than environment did on yield. This trait also had high values for heterosis (111.7%) and heterobeltiosis (60.3%) in the F₁. ■